

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR LEA

**D 4.2 Recommendations digital tools/methods for
increased dialogue and defragmentation of public
demand**

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dialogue between procurers and suppliers is vital because the failure of technology development projects is still relatively high and one of the key success factors is the smooth dialogue in between the supply and demand sides of the process. (Liu et al., 2011) One of the major lessons learned in the previous PCP project IMAILE was that the dialogue between supply and demand must start early and there should be means to ensure that the different parties are involved in the discourse on the same level (Clements & Wallin, 2017).

This deliverable D4.2 presents recommended tools for increasing dialogue and defragmentation of public demand. In this work, LEA Project identified available digital tools and methods for innovative procurement dialogue. These channels were then analysed through stakeholder interviews and expert statements on how they can be utilised effectively. This document also contains dialogue process model involving all key stakeholders of the innovative procurement and demonstrates the complexity of the innovation procurement dialogue through an example dialogue.

Supply and demand side interaction and understanding are fundamental concepts to create a sustainable, inclusive and knowledge-based growth within Learning Technology 2020 and beyond based on the following actual situation.

The demand side consists mainly of procuring authorities on local and regional level regulated by the public procurement law. In brief these organizations in general lack a deeper understanding and knowledge

about learning technologies in order to purchase smart and future-oriented innovations to improve their Education services.

The supply side (big companies, SMEs, start-ups) industry and R&I institutes risks facing “the valley of death“ to get their commercial product on the market. In brief the industry in general lack a deeper understanding of demand / user needs aligned with the societal challenges of the public sector. These are the two basic needs/ sides that LEA tasks will support by increased dialogue and knowledge transfer in WP 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this task is to establish meaningful communication channels for dialogue between supply and demand and to create recommendations for stakeholders on which channels to use for PCP/PPI dialogue. State-of-the-art of existing communicational channels for innovation procurement will be analyzed.

In this research, LEA Innovation procurement experts were asked to list online tools for innovation procurement dialogue. In addition, 24 learning technology companies were interviewed during the BETT show in January 2019. The suppliers were interviewed on how they communicate and receive feedback from end users and is there useful and meaningful channels to have a dialogue before actual product or service is on the market. Good communication between suppliers and procurers mean that suppliers are able to get in contact with customers and utilise their experiences to create demand based products. Interviewees were sampled with maximum variation, from big companies to SMEs and start-ups.

Discussions were flowed freely but the same questions were asked

- How important you think end user feedback is to your technology development?
- How you utilise the knowledge gathered from the customers?
- How you find new test users?
- Is there any special (digital) tool you have to have and maintain the dialogue with the demans?

Through these methods, following 13 tools were identified:

- Procurement forum
- EIC Community Platform
- Innovation procurement Brokers
- Procure2Innovate
- b2match
- Enterprise Europe Network
- AgID
- OpenUP Hub
- Innovation Partnership Austria
- Norwegian National Programme for Supplier Development
- TED/Hilma
- EAfip
- Hankintakeino

These tools were then analysed based on their dialogue directions and usefulness for the innovation procurement measures against the Innovation Procurement Dialogue Model.

3. INNOVATION PROCUREMENT DIALOGUE MODEL (IPD Model)

Figure 1: Schematic view of the Innovation Procurement Dialogue Model (IPD Model) for the LearnTech innovation procurement

The key communication channels and stakeholders of Innovation Procurement of Learning Technologies can be illustrated in Figure 1. The next chapters explain the key communication within the model.

3.1 Communication channels between Schools and Procurers (1↔2)

Communication between schools and procurers have been organised differently within different countries. Deliverable D3.1. LEA Procurement Analysis describes this dialogue in detail, so the focus of this deliverable is not on this communication.

3.2 Communication channels between Schools and Learntech experts (1↔3)

Schools frequently have so-called technology experts within. This could be a computer science teacher or a teacher of other similar topic or even a person assigned to be in charge of the information technology. When LearnTech experts are not already presented inside the schools, the communication between these two stakeholders happens mainly through the participation in specific targeted events open to both schools and LearnTech experts. All around Europe, either local, national or European-level events gather both schools and LearnTech experts to review state-of-the-art technologies and research.

The LEA project has identified some key events for the year 2019 with specific features for networking opportunities:

- BETT Show – 23-26/01/2019 London, UK

<https://www.bettshow.com/>

Large education technology show where the trends are presented and international suppliers, procurers, schools and experts come together.

- EDUCA – 25-26/01/2019 – Helsinki, Finland

<https://educa.messukeskus.com/?lang=en>

Comprehensive review of what's happening in education and what the professionals are talking about right now. The day-to-day work of teachers is at the heart of the event.

- Learning Technologies – 13-15/02/2019

<https://www.learningtechnologies.co.uk/>

Large education technology show where the trends are presented and international suppliers, procurers, schools and experts come together.

- LEARNTECH - 29-31/01/2019 Karlsruhe, Germany

<https://www.learntec.de/en/>

Three topic areas: schools, universities, corporates. School principals, school media advisor, and people working in education at federal state level can learn the latest news in learning tech

- EdTechXEurope 2019 - 18/06/2019 (annual) - London, United Kingdom <http://edtechxeurope.com/>

Summit connecting the global learning ecosystem

- GALA (Games and Learning Alliance) Conference - 27-29/11/2019 - Athens, Greece

<https://conf.seriousgamessociety.org/>

Researcher, developers, practitioner and stakeholders

- OEB - 27-29/11/2019 - Berlin, Germany

<https://oeb.global/>

Fostering exchange between the corporate, education and public service sector

Many of these events are also good for dialogue between all the four key stakeholder groups which means that dialogue is possible in all directions of the IPD Model.

3.3 Communication channels between Schools and Suppliers (1↔4)

In order to better understand and identify how suppliers find end-users to test new learning technologies before they enter the market, the LEA project has conducted a number of interviews to the suppliers present at the BETT show 2019 in London. The main objective was to understand how they identify and reach schools as test-users for acquiring real inputs and concrete suggestions to their products during the development stage.

While most of the suppliers referred to the importance of collecting feedback from the test-users to develop and better target their products and solutions, no specific tools for dialogue were mentioned.

Big companies had confirmed longterm connections to the customers and which meant that they needent to put effort in finding new schools for testing. Bigger companies had as well their own internal test groups and used general customer feedback to improve their products.

This indicated that specific tools to enhance dialogue between suppliers and end users were more directed to small and medium sized companies. When interviewing medium-size and small suppliers, it became evident that the need for user feedback was more urgent for them because small companies couldn't afford internal test groups. Not all the companies were interested in testing because they had so well developed product or service.

The most depended on external test users and end users' feedback were the small and medium size companies. They had an idea and many of them had been on the market only very short time. Their product were often not so developed and they were looking for test users to get valuable information to improve product/service.

The main preferred methods of communications that were identified in the BETT show's interviews are the following:

Existing customers. Existing customers is the preferred channel mentioned by the suppliers. The preference for this option is related to the fact that existing customers are already aware of previous products and can provide a more complete overview on what is missing and what they would like to be improved. At the same time, the already existent connection and familiarity also contributes to a more structured feedback and facilitates the interaction.

This option is put into practice by the offer of free-trial options for the new products during the final stages of development. The choice for existent networks can also contribute to a continuous development of the products based on a long-time shared collaboration.

School-to-school network. The second most common answer was a school-to-school network. This communication channel is used by suppliers to enlarge their existent network of contacts. By reference of existent schools and the already established network, suppliers can reach other geographically-close schools and demonstrate how their products are already being used. The same option of free trial options remains the most common answer collected during the interviews.

Networking events. The presence on networking events was also a common answer. This means that events are considered as main channels for dialogue and interaction between supply and demand in this sector. The opportunity to meet in specific public targeted events focused on learning technologies is the third option collected during the interviews.

Social media and online communication. In order to improve the visibility of the products and enhance their image, suppliers use social media and online materials to reach their target groups. This option allows to spread the presence of the products available online with a direct link to free trial options to test new products and solutions that are already available on the market.

Internal development teams. Some suppliers of medium-large dimension mentioned that, in order to test new solutions and products before reaching the market, they do not need to directly contact test-users because they have the capacity and the means for internal testing. While this solution does not bring a real context feedback from schools, suppliers with more capacity mentioned this as a preference for a cost-efficiency reason. However, they still highlight the need for feedback in real conditions which are made available through their products and which existent customers are able to provide.

Indirect communication (1 → 2 → 4 or 1 → 3 → 4):

3.4 Communication channels between Suppliers and Procurers (2↔4)

Branding and lobbying actions were mentioned by medium-sized suppliers present at the BETT show as a solution provided to attract procurers and share their products. This happens via a number of private actions and invitation-only events to present to procurers their respective products and influence their decision. For procurers the participation in these actions and being aware of what is new on the market allows them to have a better understanding and better target and prepare the respective procurement of products more relevant for them. At the same time, it also opens a

window of opportunity to share with suppliers the needs and feedback collected from schools and influence the development of new solutions to face those challenges.

4. DIGITAL TOOLS FOR INNOVATION PROCUREMENT DIALOGUE

Open dialogue between demand and supply side are fundamental for the success of the preparatory activities for launching an innovative procurement call and for the procurement process itself (after the its awarding phase). Besides, involvement of end-users is deemed necessary for the success of the research and innovation activities.

Thus, LEA will devote huge efforts in designing and implementing opportunities for concrete and constructive industry dialogues, where procurers, suppliers, researchers, end-users and other interested stakeholders will find the tools and the opportunity to be part of the process of shaping the challenges and needs and the visions for the future in education and learning technology. In this chapter we present the identified tools for the innovation procurement dialogue and analyse the tools and their usefulness.

4.1 Procurement Forum

Figure 2: Procurement forum

Website

<https://procurement-forum.eu/>

Description of the digital tool

The Procurement Forum is an online tool to facilitate procurement professionals from across Europe (and beyond) to connect and exchange on a range of topics relevant to public procurement.

Stakeholders/users

- public procurers
- procurement experts
- policy makers

Functionalities

- Users can post questions or share information to public space or groups on specific topics. Other users can be tagged in posts.
- Users can create new groups and invite users to participate in these, and can share and store documents within groups
- Users can access and upload resources to the Resource Database
- Users can post events in the events calendar.

Type of Dialogue

- Procurer - to - procurer (or with experts)

LEA experts' evaluation comments

- Free to use
- Provides private digital space to facilitate dialogue between procurers
- Not really supporting the supply & demand dialogue (only common demand)

4.2 EIC Community Platform

European Commission > EASME > SME Instrument > EIC Community Platform

EIC Community Platform

PAGE CONTENT

What is it the EIC Community?

What is ScaleUp EU?

What is it the EIC Community?

The [EIC Community Platform](#) is a virtual meeting-place where companies funded by the [European Innovation Council \(EIC\) pilot](#) can connect, share their experiences and leverage potential business partnerships. They can also find investors through the find investors [ScaleUp EU](#) tool.

Figure 3: EIC community platform

Website

<https://community-smei.easme-web.eu/>

Description of the digital tool

EIC Community Platform is a virtual meeting-place where companies funded by the European Innovation Council (EIC) pilot can connect, share their experiences and leverage potential business partnerships. They can also find investors through the investor ScaleUp EU tool.

Stakeholders/users

- EIC pilot-funded small companies
- investors

Functionalities

Groups provide members with a space to connect, share ideas and foster opportunities in public or private groups, between members with shared interests and purposes. Here you find information, events and group discussions under a specific theme created by a group

Type of Dialogue

two-way dialogue supply and investors

LEA tool evaluation

Owned by the European Commission

Not generally used by public procurers.

4.3 Innovation Procurement Brokers

Figure 4: Innovation Procurement Brokers

Website

<https://www.innovation-procurement.org/projects/innovation-procurement-brokers/>

Description of the digital tool

Innovation Procurement Brokers facilitates procurement of innovative goods and services by linking public buyers with innovative companies.

It is not a digital tool, but a 2-year COSME funded project (August 2018 - August 2020), which aims to test innovation procurement brokerage approaches at regional and European levels, and scaling up pilots to a European level.

It plans to engage 20 public buyers, 40 suppliers, host 5 needs assessment workshops, 5 market engagement events, and finally have 1 combined Innobrokers model for future activities.

Stakeholders/users

- Public procurers
- SMEs and start-ups
- Organisations supporting innovation procurement (experts)

Functionalities

- testing innovation procurement brokerage approaches at regional and European levels
- supporting and carrying out assessment of public authority needs
- Engaging with start-ups and SMEs across Europe to find innovative solutions to needs

Type of Dialogue

procurers, supplier and experts engaged in dialogue

LEA tool evaluation

- Opportunity for collaboration (i.e. to learn from pilots and feed LEA experience into scaling up of successful brokerage models)
- The resulting digital tool will not be ready in time for the LEA project (but could support future activities resulting from LEA)
- Schools are not involved, only procurers

4.4 Procure2Innovate

Figure 5: Procure2Innovate

Website

<http://procure2innovate.eu/>

Description of digital tool

European network of competence centres for innovation procurement.

Stakeholders/users

innovation procurement competence centres

Functionalities

Gathers together innovation procurement expertise from 12 countries (Austria, Germany, Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, Estonia, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Lithuania, Finland) facilitating flow of information and experience both up from national levels, and down from European level to local level.

Type of dialogue

- procurers <> experts

LEA tool evaluation

- provides mechanism to increase innovation procurement knowledge at a national and local level across Europe
- borderline to be considered as a “tool for dialogue”

4.5 b2match

Figure 6:b2match

Website

<https://www.b2match.com>

Description of the digital tool

b2match, is a digital platform aiming to foster networking during events. b2match enables the attendees of one specific event, to register on this platform and to schedule personal meeting with other participants.

Stakeholders/users

This tool can be used by all the stakeholders involved in LEA process when they are participating in a relevant event.

Functionalities

This matchmaking process makes sure that participants can request, manage and schedule meetings efficiently. On this platform, you can see

who is participating and the respective profiles, request a meeting with one specific attendee, choose the time of the meeting, and exchange messages.

Type of Dialogue

This tool permits to look for specific person/profile and to schedule meetings during networking events.

LEA tool evaluation

- useful and important tools for LEA stakeholders within Learntech and EdTech events.
- facilitates the interaction of LEA stakeholders with specific participants according to their needs within events.
- Very general, no field specific

4.6 Enterprise Europe Network

Figure 7: Enterprise Europe Network

Website

<https://een.ec.europa.eu/>

Description of the digital tool

The Enterprise Europe Network helps businesses innovate and grow on an international scale. It is the world's largest support network for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with international ambitions. The network covered more than 60 countries worldwide and more than 3000 experts from 600 organisations including technology poles, innovation support organisations, universities and research institutes, regional development organisations and chambers of commerce and industry.

Stakeholders/users

Suppliers and Procurers

Functionalities

Being a member of the EEN network permits to get advice from experts to grow their business. Furthermore, it helps to find business partner with the largest online database of business opportunities.

Type of Dialogue

- Publish your business idea or plan
- Getting advices from experts
- Find partners by publishing you announce on the website

LEA tool evaluation

- Good solution to gain more visibility
- Expand networks at European level
- Allow exchanges within the members
- No involvement of end-users and experts
- Quite general, not specific on a subject

4.7 Agenzia per l'Italia Digitale (AgID)

Figure 8: AgID

Website

<https://www.agid.gov.it/it/agenzia>

Description of the digital tool

The main purpose of the Agency is to guarantee the achievement of the Italian digital agenda objectives and contribute to the diffusion of information and communication technologies, with the aim of fostering innovation and economic growth. AgID supports digital innovation and promotes the dissemination of digital skills, also in collaboration with international, national and local institutions and bodies.

Stakeholders/users

Public administration in Italy and abroad
Suppliers (SMEs, companies and startups)

Functionalities

Manage the IT coordination of central, regional and local administration;
Ensure homogeneity of public information systems and the integration of these systems at EU level; Plan and coordinate strategic and/or cross-sectoral initiatives of national interest; Disseminate information and communication technologies to foster innovation and economic, social and cultural growth; Participate in the implementation of European programmes in order to attract, raise and monitor funds focussed on innovation policies; Promote the definition and development of strategic research and innovation projects related to the implementation of the Italian and European Digital Agenda, also in line with the EU Horizon2020 programme; Support all actions aimed at improving digital technologies and services to boost the economic and social growth of the country, according to the pillars of the European Digital Agenda.

Type of Dialogue

Information channel

LEA tool evaluation

- Specific to Italy
- Can be helpful for the dissemination activities

4.8 OpenUP Hub

Figure 9: OpenUP Hub

Website

<https://www.openuphub.eu/>

Description of the digital tool

OpenUP Hub is an open, dynamic and collaborative knowledge environment that systematically captures, organizes and categorizes research outcomes, best practices, tools, and guidelines relevant to review-dissemination-assessment phases of the research lifecycle through the prism of Open Science. OpenUP Hub is an integrated solution that supports the community needs by offering the right tools for the relevant stakeholders to open up science. the research lifecycle through the prism of Open Science. OpenUP Hub is an integrated solution that supports the community needs by offering the right tools for the relevant stakeholders to open up science.

Stakeholders/users

- Stakeholders engaged in the research lifecycle: researchers, young scholars, educators, publishers, R&I project members, policy makers & funders, IT providers and citizens.

Functionalities

- Toolbox: The OpenUP Hub provides an inventory of selected tools addressing your needs & questions
- Blog: Collect & promote interesting articles & point of views on Open Science.
- Calendar: Events and workshops that are relevant to open peer review, innovative dissemination, alternative impact assessment & Open Science world.
- Members: Meet, connect & exchange with other community members also interested and active in Open Science.

Type of Dialogue

- Provide advice from experts
- Communication and dissemination platform for events and news

LEA tool evaluation

- Allow the exchange between all stakeholders of education, research
- Can collect feedback

4.9 Innovation Partnership Austria

Figure 10: Innovation Partnership Austria

Website

<https://innovationspartnerschaft.at/>

Description of the digital tool

Online platform giving public buyers chance to consult the market. Managed by the Austrian Centre for Procurement Innovation. Support public procurers in innovation-promoting contracts, thus increasing the total number of innovative public procurement deals in the long term.

Stakeholders/users

- Suppliers (companies)
- Public administration in Austria
- Experts

Functionalities

- Free services
- Challenges for companies and public administration
- Market research: Companies: develop their product and introduce it to a public administration. Public administration: find a solution and invite companies, start-ups, citizens and citizens to develop innovative solution strategies.
- Ideas competitions: Companies: submit an idea, have feedback, everyone can participate. Public administration: invite innovative companies, start-ups, citizens and citizens to an idea competition - from the development of innovative concepts to promising prototypes.
- Solutions: Submit in find solutions

Type of Dialogue

- Publishing, for companies, their products or services
- Find, from the market, a solution for specific public administration and procurers' challenges.
- Find suppliers for their solutions on the market (procurers)

LEA tool evaluation

- Easy access
- Can publish call
- Specific to Austria

4.10 Norwegian National Programme for Supplier development

Innovative anskaffelser

Hva blir det neste?

[Til forsiden](#)

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About Innovative Procurements

In Norway, public agencies procure goods and services for close to 58 billion Euros every year. Innovative Procurements is a new method for public procurements. In Innovative Procurements requesting pre-defined solutions from the market is discouraged. Instead, needs and functions are communicated to the market, which in turn responds on how to best

Figure 11: Norwegian National Programme for Supplier Development

Website

<http://innovativeanskaffelser.no/about/>

Description of the digital tool

The initiative acts as a broker between several procurement initiatives, and buyers are supported to identify joint needs. Mapping and defining needs are emphasized, the market is invited for dialogue, and challenged to come up with smart solutions. The National Programme for Supplier Development is set up to accelerate innovations and development of new solutions through the strategic use of public procurement, while at the same time contributing to new market opportunities for these innovations.

Stakeholders/users

The programme is a joint collaboration by three significant entities with unique strengths, networks and focus areas – representing both the public and private sector.

Difi (Agency for Public Management and eGovernment) provides pertinent support in developing relevant tools and guidance on public procurement
Norwegian Association of Local and Regional Authorities (KS) naturally provides the link to both local and regional authorities and stimulate actors in the direction towards innovative public procurements;

Confederation of Norwegian Enterprise (NHO) provides the link to the private sector actors.

Innovasjon Norway (IN) is the Norwegian Government's instrument for innovation and development of Norwegian enterprises and industry.

The Research Council of Norway (FR) serves as the chief advisory body for the government authorities on research policy issues

Functionalities

Rigging the market potential from the onset to allow scale

Facilitating and brokering in 9 Innovation Partnerships

Type of Dialogue

Intermediary between demand and supply

LEA tool evaluation

- Can be supported by relevant Norwegian National bodies

4.11 Hilma – Finnish connection to TED

The screenshot shows the HILMA website interface. At the top left is the HILMA logo and the text 'Julkiset hankinnat'. On the right, there are login fields for 'Tunnus' and 'Salasana', and a 'Sisään' button. Below the login fields are links for 'Unohtuiko tunnus tai salasana?' and 'Rekisteröidy'. A navigation bar contains links for 'Etusivu', 'På svenska', 'Palaute', 'Usein kysyttyä', 'Yhteystiedot', and 'Ulkoiset linkit'. The main content area features a search bar with the label 'Hakusana(t)' and a 'HAE' button. To the right of the search bar is a 'Tervetuloa HILMAN sivuille!' message. Below this, there is a section titled 'Ajankohtaista' with several news items, including 'Huomioitavaksi vuodenvaihteessa' (5.12.2018), 'HILMAN vuoden 2017 tilastot julkaistu' (29.11.2018), 'CPV-koodien käyttö muuttuu' (8.11.2018), 'CPV-koodien käyttö muuttuu HILMAN päivityksessä' (5.9.2018), and 'Hilma uudistuu' (7.6.2018). There is also a note about the 'Julkisten hankintojen neuvontayksikkö on laatinut ohjeistuksen komission ESPD-'. The right side of the page has a 'Uusimmat ilmoitukset' section with a link to 'Hankintalainsäädännön mukaiset ilmoitukset' and 'Muut ilmoitukset'. Below this, it shows 'Ilmoituksia: 3444 näytä kaikki' and a list of filters: '1-50 51-100 101-150 151-200 201-250 251-300 301-350 351-400 401-450 451-500 501-550 ...'. At the bottom, there are tabs for 'Julkaistu', 'Tariousten', and 'Ilmoituksen nimi'.

Figure 12: Hilma

Website

<https://www.hankintailmoitukset.fi/fi/>

Description of the digital tool

Hilma is a free digital tool where procurers can publish their call for public procurement. Service is provided by ministry of economic affairs and employment of Finland.

Hilma provides companies real time knowledge of ongoing procurements and foreknowledge of upcoming procurements. Hilma is used as a national digital channel for procurements and for those procurements cross EU threshold (over 225 000euros).

Stakeholders/users

- Procurers such as public organizations and churches
 - Ministry of economic affairs and employment of Finland
 - Suppliers
-
- Functionalities
 - Procurer can publish a call
 - Suppliers can view calls

Type of Communication

Public publishing channel for calls

LEA tool evaluation

- Tool is free
- Easy to publish call for public procurement
- Easy access to view public procurements
- Registration is needed to fill in the call
- Valid calls can be viewed without registration.
- No possibility to interact
- Two sided information, no experts nor end users in the dialogue

4.12 European Assistance for Innovation Procurement – *eafip*

Figure 13: Eafip

Website

<http://eafip.eu/about/>

Description of the digital tool

The *eafip* initiative implemented a Toolkit for an easy-to-use support and hands-on guidance in preparing and implementing an innovation procurement. The Toolkit to provide support to policy makers in designing PCP and PPI strategies, and to procurers and their legal departments in implementing such procurements.

Stakeholders/users

- Launched by the European Commission Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology ([DG Connect](#))

- Implemented by [STELLA Consulting](#) and [Corvers Procurement Services](#).
- Users: policy makers, public procurers and legal services

Functionalities

- The *eafip* Toolkit consists of three modules:
- The *eafip* Toolkit consists of three modules:
- Module 1: A strategic module addressed to policy makers, providing economic and case evidence about the impacts and benefits of PCP and PPI, together with concrete guidance on how to embed PCP and PPI into innovation strategies;
- Module 2: An operational module addressed to public procurers aimed at clarifying the pre-requisites and key steps to design and implement an innovation procurement process (PCP and PPI); and
- Module 3: A legal / operational module addressed to legal services aimed at clarifying legal issues and provide practical 'how-to' guidelines, supported by templates.

Type of Dialogue

- Assistance to procurers to implement PCP/PPI
- Support to policy makers in designing PCP/PPI

LEA tool evaluation

- The *eafip* initiative is over (it lasted from 2015 to 2018) but the learning toolkit is still available online.
- Useful to help in preparing an innovation procurement

4.13 Hankintakeino

Figure 14: Hankintakeino

website

<https://www.hankintakeino.fi/en>

Description of the digital tool

KEINO supports and helps Finnish public procurement experts and authorities with the development of sustainable and innovative procurement. KEINO is a network-based consortium, whose founding members responsible for the operation and co-development are Motiva Ltd, the Association of Finnish Local and Regional Authorities, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd, The Finnish Funding Agency for Innovation – Business Finland, the Finnish Environment Institute SYKE, Hansel Ltd, KL-Kuntahankinnat Ltd and the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra.

Stakeholders/users

- Suppliers and procurers

Functionalities

KEINO supports and helps Finnish public procurement experts and authorities with the development of sustainable and innovative procurement.

The main objectives of the year 2019 are the number of innovative and sustainable procurements in Finland increases, public procurement is recognised and actively used as a management tool and contracting entities openly disseminate information on their own experiences and learn from one another.

Type of Dialogue

Keino promotes better public procurement by providing experts who help and advice on the every phase of the procurement process.

LEA tool evaluation

- Free service
- High quality expertise
- Easy to contact
- Free trainings

5. CONCLUSIONS

Following table 1 includes the LEA recommendations for supply & demand dialogue. Innovation procurement stakeholders can utilize this table and report to identify useful tools for their supply & demand dialogue.

Table 1: Innovation procurement dialogue tools summary

Innovation Procurement Tools	Procurers <-> Procurers	Schools <-> Schools	Schools <-> Procurers	Schools <-> LT experts	Schools <-> Suppliers	Procurers <-> LT experts	Procurers <-> Suppliers	Suppliers <-> LT experts
Procurement forum	X					X		
EIC Community Platform							X	
Innovation procurement Brokers							X	
Procure2Innovate	X							
b2match	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Enterprise Europe Network							X	X
AgID	X							
OpenUP Hub	X			X		X		X
Innovation Partnership Austria							X	X
Norwegian National Programme for Supplier Development							X	
TED/Hilma	X						X	
EAFip	X							
Hankintakein	X					X		
European events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

In this Supply & Demand dialogue research, we interviewed 24 Learning technology companies and expert reviewed 13 identified digital tools for innovation procurement dialogue. The summary of the analysis shows that

there is some European digital tools available for the defragmentation of the public demand within Europe such as the Procurement forum, procure2innovate, OpenUPHub etc. Mostly these tools are presenting information on the innovation procurement but they are not necessarily used to their full potential. European LT networking events such as the BETT show, Learning Technologies or Online Educa Berlin provide excellent opportunities for the supply & demand dialogue face-to-face. From the Suppliers' interviews we also learned that they mainly use the following channels for supply & demand dialogue:

- Contacting existing customers
- School networks
- Networking events
- Social media
- Internal R&D teams

The Digital tools identified in the LEA research can benefit SMEs and start-ups the most. Bigger companies have their own testing departments and do not test in real classroom environments.

Learning technology field organises a large number of annual conferences and networking events which are important occasions for supply and demand dialogue. However, the efficiency of using events depends on which personnel have been sent to represent organisations in this particular event. E.g. the sales persons might not be knowledgeable enough to discuss features of technology in-depth.

Based on the summary table 1 we can also interpret that schools are often 'left out' from the innovation procurement supply & demand dialogue. There clearly is a demand for a digital tool to accelerate the dialogue between schools and other stakeholders of the innovation procurement

process. Concepts such as LEA School Labs (see D2.1 for more information) can assist the dialogue between suppliers and schools, but enforced dialogue measures are needed to get the end users' voice heard in the supply & demand dialogue of innovation procurement.

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